

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE INNOVATIVE POSITION OF DISTANCE LEARNING IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract

Compared to traditional forms of education, distance education optimally develops students' independence, activity, awareness, and creativity, effectively solves the strategic issues facing modern teacher training in the information society. The irreplaceable role and place of increasing the quality and efficiency of higher education also highlights the relevance of distance education. It is also advantageous in terms of creating the same opportunity for them to study regardless of their place of residence, health status, standard of living and financial support. On the other hand, distance learning is also very cost-effective. It provides an opportunity to study without incurring additional costs (transportation, housing and other costs).

These factors indicate the importance and relevance of the topic chosen for research. Integration into the world, globalization, rapid information processes cause significant changes in all areas of modern society and increase the role of human capital as the main factor in the successful development of the state. Changes in the education system, especially in higher education, the need for capable, competitive specialists who can meet the needs of society and the state, along with their self-education, have also brought up the issue of informatization of education.

The application of distance education technologies in all areas was the focus of national leader Heydar Aliyev's attention years ago as an urgent issue, and in this regard, he adopted the "National Strategy on Information and Communication Technologies for the Development of the Republic of Azerbaijan" covering the years 2003-2012 [5]. . As a continuation of this, the declaration of 2013 as the "Year of Information and Communication Technologies" in the Republic of Azerbaijan by the head of the country, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, and the laying of the foundation of the University of Information Technologies are among the steps aimed at the informatization of the society and, accordingly, the training of educated and competent specialists.

At the same time, starting from 2007-2008, Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University started using electronic test technologies for innovative development of education, current and final evaluation of education quality. With the joint initiative of the university's administrative, professor and teaching staff, technical specialists, the holding of test exams became more organized, which gave students the opportunity to check their knowledge more accurately using electronic resources [2].

In addition, the experience of Azerbaijan on the informatization of education was presented at the "ITU World Telecom 2009" forum held in Geneva from October 5 to 9, 2009. At the events held in connection with this forum, representatives of many countries were informed about the creation of the Azerbaijan Education Network (AZEDUNET), the Information and Resource Center, the "Electronic School", as well as the National Education Program, and the achievements of the country in the field of application of information technologies were demonstrated [6, p. 125].

The transition to the information society makes the problem of the formation of modern thinking in the new generation even more urgent, creates the need for fundamental changes in education, and creates a fundamental basis for students' adaptation to education and strengthening of distance learning tendencies.

Keywords: improvement, information, distance learning, new approaches

In modern conditions, young personnel must master not only the knowledge of their specialty, but also the latest achievements of science and technology, be able to use distance education tools, and search for new sources of information to improve themselves every day [10, p.63].

In recent years, the widespread use of computer technology in education has greatly facilitated the organization of distance education for students. Thus, information and computer technologies optimize educational discipline, distance education, activities, learning foreign languages, independent training, deep learning of professional knowledge, and the educational process of conducting educational work. The use of information technologies allows students to be actively involved in work, to acquire knowledge,

and to increase the level of distance education and professionalism.

Distance education ability is developed during independent activity through information sources, in search of information as an ability determined by the psychological and intellectual indicators of each student.

The main goal of the educational reform implemented in our country is to make distance education and independent activity of students one of the centers of gravity of education. From this point of view, independent, creative thinking, universal knowledge and modern thinking, broad-minded, competitive and enterprising personnel preparation is one of the main goals of the education system [8, p. 236]. In this regard, the main goal of the application of

distance education technologies in education is to create interest in self-education in students, to prepare them for this activity in a systematic, consistent and purposeful way, to instill in them the necessary skills for independent activity. Thus, the introduction of distance learning into the educational environment leads to a radical change in the learning process. Based on this, one of the national priorities in our republic is the informatization of education.

Mr. President puts forward the idea that only if this happens, the young generation can be formed as professional personnel in accordance with the requirements of the time. In his opinion, both material and technical provision and modernization of the learning and teaching process should be done at the same level in every educational institution. Only in this case, it is possible to achieve the desired result. In world experience, even the most prestigious universities are never satisfied with the status they have earned. He is constantly striving for innovation.

Therefore, reforms in higher schools should be permanent. In other words, constantly following scientific innovations, understanding them, establishing mutual relations with higher schools with advanced experience can encourage our education to reach the world level in the true sense of the word [3, p.91].

In the conditions of informatization of education, the main criteria for having the skills of organizing distance education activities can be listed as follows:

- to create an independent problem based on the obtained information or to be able to see the problem in a normal state;
- to propose a method for data analysis, collection and processing;
- draw conclusions and see the possibilities of practical application of the obtained results;
- evaluate the results of their work and prove their correctness;
- to apply the possibilities of information technologies.

Thus, the introduction of distance learning into the educational environment leads to a radical change in the learning process. Based on this, one of the national priorities in our republic is the informatization of education. Even in highly developed countries, the main financial resources are directed to education and training of ICT literate professionals.

Experience shows that the development of distance education-based education plays an important role in solving a number of the following issues:

- increases knowledge and experience to live and operate in modern society;
- bringing new forms and methods to the learning process increases the quality of education;
- gives everyone at any age the opportunity to study and improve their knowledge, etc.

Informatization of education is the process of providing education with modern information technologies, along with theoretical and practical work carried out in educational institutions in the psychological and pedagogical direction. Informatization is an important condition for the

implementation and management of educational activities, and an important factor for the development of society.

The process of distance planning and organization of education in higher education institutions begins with equipping educational institutions with distance education technologies, preparing electronic textbooks and personnel in this field. In the preparation of personnel for the organization and management of the distance education-based learning process, the creation of a teaching-methodical base, the preparation of teaching-methodical literature, and the organization of information infrastructure are important issues.

The President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the approval of the tasks defined in the field of information and communication technologies and the "Action Plan regarding the declaration of 2013 as the "Year of Information and Communication Technologies" in the Republic of Azerbaijan" based on the "Azerbaijan 2020: Vision of the Future" Development Concept. On March 28, 2013, it adopted Order No. 2815.

As we know, lack of computers is the main factor that slows down the process of planning and organizing distance education in higher education institutions. In accordance with the solution of this problem, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, approved the "Program for provision of general education schools in the Republic of Azerbaijan with information and communication technologies" by the order dated August 15, 2004. After the implementation of this program, local computer production was stimulated, software for the management of educational institutions was developed, electronic textbook portals were created, many educational institutions were provided with access to the Internet, etc. [6].

The process of remote education plays an important role in improving the quality of education, providing opportunities for students to receive higher education, creating self-education, interest and inclination to study, and training national personnel in the field of ICT as an important strategic issue. ir. Today, the establishment of the Institute of Information Technologies under ANAS, the preparation of intellectual projects based on ICT in various fields, the creation and development of computer networks and systems are among our achievements. In the future, success in education, as well as in other fields, will depend on the development of information and communication technologies and their correct use.

Remote education in higher education institutions provides high-quality educational services in the following content:

- required information remains in memory for a long time;
- teacher's self-education, qualification improvement, attestation, etc. gives favorable opportunities in matters;
- the acquisition of knowledge becomes easier, it creates conditions for the use of rapidly updated information, self-education activities, etc.

As people around the world adapt to new ways of working, studying, and socializing, we see new trends

emerge and evolve. In 2020, FutureLearn commissioned YouGov to conduct global research to explore the future of learning. The main themes of this study were personal development and career aspirations, the power of education and online learning, and expectations for future education. According to research, self-education in the digital age is easier than ever. Much of this is due to round-the-clock news and access to various websites that provide a constant stream of information. Perhaps not surprisingly, social media plays an important role in the organization of distance education. The study found that Millennials (those born between 1981 and 1996) and Generation Z (those born after 1997) use every platform to self-educate. For example, 37% of Generation Z and 22% of Millennials use social networks for learning [99]. Referring to this information, it should be noted that information and communication technologies have an irreplaceable role in the development of self-education.

It is an undeniable fact that the development of human potential and the level of knowledge of countries that pay attention to education and its organization are higher. In recent years, in order to further improve the level of education in our country, schools that meet new modern requirements have been built, the material and technical base of educational institutions has been strengthened, textbooks have been updated, and strategies and concepts that promote the development of education have been adopted. Therefore, according to the level of literacy, Azerbaijan is ahead of many neighboring countries.

Despite the work done in the direction of the development of education, there are still problems that have not been fully resolved. One of them is that distance education, which is specified in the Law "On Education" as a form of education, is not widely applied in the field of higher education. For example, in connection with the coronavirus pandemic, which is one of the important problems of the current year, there was a need for online education in educational institutions. Although the teachers tried to conduct online lessons with programs such as "Teams", "Zoom", "Ekurs.az", they could not achieve the desired results. Despite all the planned efforts, the problems that arise in the first period are the lack of an internet line at the homes of many students, the lack of psychological preparation of teachers and students for online classes, the lack of experience in the field of online communication, the lack of the same skills in using IT equipment, the lack of material and technical bases in higher education institutions and other objectives. was related to factors. However, in developed countries, the distance education system has penetrated the entire sphere of society faster.

For this, in unexpected situations like this, the most important goal and task of all higher education institutions should be to ensure that distance learning classes are as content and quality as face-to-face classes, and their integration. However, we should especially note that in the last two years we have been able to achieve results that we have not achieved in ten years in the field of distance education.

Distance education is one of the forms of continuous education and realizes the rights of people to receive education and information. It expands the educational opportunities of citizens within the country. Distance learning allows schoolchildren, students, unemployed, military and legal entities to benefit from the scientific and educational potential of leading universities, institutes, professional development and professional exchange centers. Distance learning provides conditions for additional education in addition to basic activities and education.

After the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic, teaching in all educational institutions was temporarily suspended from March 3, 2020, in order to prevent the virus. In order to overcome the interruptions in education, a form of distance education has been introduced. Classes are organized through various platforms and applications, teachers conduct training online. Basic in organizing online classes Skype, Zoom, Microsoft Teams programs are widely used [4, p.58].

During the organization of distance education, the solution of additional problems in the organization of the educational process of the university also reveals the following needs:

- creation of a pedagogical theory of lifelong personality development based on the achievements of psychology, sociology, cultural studies, philosophy for the sake of ensuring the unity of learning, education and development processes;
- comprehensive integration of higher education institutions with priority areas of scientific research at the initiative of both state and private organizations;
- comprehensive application of new information technologies in the educational process of the university;
- training of mobile, entrepreneurial, creative thinking specialists who are ready for lifelong, continuous self-education [11].

We analyzed several works to determine the degree of elaboration of the dissertation work. Talibov, Y. "Teachers' self-study program on pedagogy", Mahmudova, R.M. "Possibilities and ways of student independent work in higher school", Hashimova, A.Ş. "The system of self-education of students and young people", Agayev, A.A. "Selected pedagogical works", Ilyasov, M.I. "Choice of Profession, Specialization", Rustamov, F.A. Dadashova, T.Y. "High school pedagogy", Aliyeva, Z.I. "Pedagogy", Jabrayilov, I.H. "Azerbaijani education in the period of independence: theoretical and practical aspects" and the works of other Azerbaijani researchers have widely commented on the issues of self-education and independent work. Ahmadov, I.B., Abbasov, A.M. Alizadeh, M.N. Seyidzadeh, E.V. Musayev, I.K., Ilyasov, M.I., Aliguliyeva, R.M. Mahmudova, R.Sh., Hamidov, S.S., Karimov, S., Farzana, C.G., Bunyatov, A.R. and others have extensively addressed issues related to distance education in their works.

Foreign educators Ismail, G. Seda, Ch. Buquet, D., Filizok, R., Özer, B., Toker, M.M., Jacques, D., Samaras, A.P., Sergio, S. Fabio, A. Maura, C. Luisa, F. et al. Distance learning in their work, self-education,

learning how to learn have been touched upon. Zair Bek, E.S., Yakimanskaya, I.S., Pyazova, L.M., Obraztsov, P.I., Sagitova, R.R., Stashkevich, I.R., Sukhanov, P.V., Шахова, И.Н., Шуклина, Е.А. Osmolovskaya, I.M., Shvyrev, B.C., Zharinov, V.M., Yakovleva, A.L., Koltsova, N.V. and other Russian pedagogues have widely commented on the issue of distance learning in higher education institutions [13].

The main goal of the research is to study the main criteria for the development of the organization of students' distance learning in higher education institutions.

In accordance with the set goal, the following main tasks of the research are defined:

1. To determine the degree of development of the problem and the socio-historical preconditions for the development of students' educational activities in the conditions of planning and organizing education in a distance form.

2. To theoretically substantiate the motivational-action approach that determines the development strategy of students' educational activities in the conditions of distance planning and organization of education in higher educational institutions.

3. To prepare and theoretically justify the pedagogical concept for the development of distance learning of students in the conditions of the development of education in a distance form.

4. To develop a model for the development of distance activity of students in the conditions of informatization of education, to identify examples and to justify its technology.

5. To identify and justify the possibilities of creating optimal conditions for the development of distance learning activities of students by creating a distance learning environment in the university.

6. To determine the success of the process of development of distance activity of students in the conditions of informatization of education, to develop possible criteria and indicators and to theoretically justify them.

The theoretical basis of the research is the study of the experience of foreign countries and Azerbaijan in the field of distance education activities of students in the conditions of distance education planning and organization in higher education institutions, the study of the basic principles of the modern theory of personality development and self-education activities, the accepted concepts and strategies for the organization of education in distance form [4, p. 278]. The theoretical importance of the research is the creation of a work system for the development of distance learning activities in the conditions of remote activity of students in the conditions of distance organization and planning of education in higher educational institutions, which are of great socio-economic importance in the preparation of future teachers. In the study, the theoretical propositions related to distance education, personality development and the use of information technologies were included, and the work was carried out from the point of view of the methodological regulation of the process of development of distance education activities of

students in the conditions of the distance activity of students in the conditions of the organization and planning of education in the form of distance education in higher education institutions. The presented motivation-action approach is theoretically justified [7, p. 367].

The complexity and versatility of the researched subject requires relying on a system of approaches aimed at the unity of personality, activity, society and cognition, which allows to present various facts, regularities and dependencies of the development of students' ICT skills in the form of a single theory. The methodological guidelines for the research are: a systematic approach to the planning and organization of higher education institutions in a remote form and to determine the systematic development of students' remote activity in the conditions of informatization of education in this direction; action approach - empirical (test, observation, survey, conversation, interview); statistical (data collection, statistical summary, processing, generalization and description); pedagogical diagnosis; experimental (conducting experimental studies, expert evaluations) [9, p.96].

At the current stage of development of the society, in the conditions of the organization and planning of distance education in higher education institutions, it has emerged as a necessity to reconsider the role of distance education of students. Thus, the process of development of distance education of students is one of the factors that meet the needs of the individual, society and the state [13]. Targeted distance education activity is an activity guided by the needs and motives of the students themselves, expressed by setting independent tasks, searching for ways to achieve them in order to gain new knowledge and work experience. The organization of education remotely gives every student the freedom to choose his own learning path throughout his life. The organization and planning of education in a distance form in higher education institutions is an interconnected structure that is combined with general educational goals, focused on the needs and opportunities of students, the structure and content of education, the integration of pedagogical technologies. implies the unity of components [1, p.56].

The pedagogical concept of the development of students' educational activity in the conditions of distance organization and planning of education in higher educational institutions is based on the set of the mentioned provisions:

- within the educational process of the university, the activity of distance education provides not only acquired knowledge, skills, habits, but also individual distance education and personal development throughout life;

- the university's distance learning process involves the gradual formation of the student's subjective position, and motivation is based on the activity approach;

- the application of information technologies to the distance learning process of the university is based on the principles of their integration with pedagogical technologies;

- the development of students' lessons in a distance form of educational activity takes place in the process of solving problems and determining ways to achieve goals based on conscious, independent choice, evaluating the final result, synthesizing cognitive, personal and subject experience obtained in certain situations close to reality;

- continuous distance learning of students takes place under the influence of an innovative educational environment.

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